

IMPACT OF ANIMAL HUSBANDRY ON CULTURE AND RELIGIOUS
RELATIONS IN ANCIENT NAKHSHAB

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Abstract. This article analyzes the influence of cattle-breeders on the ancient Nakhshab area, based on the materials of tombs and fortresses belonging to nomads from the Bronze to the early Middle Ages, studied in the oasis. It also provides information on the religious views of the Nakhshab oasis, the largest cultural oasis in Central Asia in the early Middle Ages, and the surrounding area.

Keywords: Nakhshab, herdsman, Samarkand, Kesh, temple, Arab invasion, religious tolerance.

Introduction. The contribution of our ancestors to the development of human civilization in the modern Kashkadarya oasis, where mankind has lived since ancient times due to favorable natural conditions, is invaluable. In the wide valley below the Kashkadarya River, there were very fertile lands for agriculture and cattle breeding. The lower part forms a large pasture complex adjacent to southwestern Turkmenistan. This has been the cause of the first economic achievements of our ancestors in the oasis since ancient times.

From ancient times, the mass influx of nomadic pastoralists into the agricultural oases of Central Asia in the steppes of Eurasia led to the settlement of some groups of the population. This situation is also characteristic of the ancient Nakhshab region. This process has played an important role in the development of the oasis, the development of new lands, the transformation of the population into densely populated areas, the revival of economic life and the strengthening of socio-political

and ethno-cultural ties. At that time, Nakhshab was part of the ancient Sogdian Zarafshan oasis.

The Bronze Age burial mounds of many herders in the oasis have the characteristics of the steppe-Andronova communities. For example, in the Dashti Qazi cemetery near the town of Panjikent, most of the corpses were buried lying to the left, with their legs bent and their heads facing west. [1] Along with the body, the tombs contain pottery, various ornaments, ocher, as well as coal dust and fragments. The pottery is handmade, and most of them are in the form of pots, various, triangular, spruce-shaped notches and notches. Pottery from peasant communities was also found here.

The pottery found in the short-term settlements of cattle breeders in the Gujayli, Big and Small Tuzkan and Mohandarya rivers in the lower part of Zarafshan is almost identical to the materials belonging to the Andronovo communities. reaffirms the scientific hypothesis that In the words of academician AA Askarov, "this is the first time that the Turkic-speaking steppe steppes of the Zarafshan valley began to mix with the ancient agricultural communities of Sugdiyabon" [2].

The gradual settlement of the steppe population and their rapprochement with the local population as a result of various cultural ties have further revived the socio-economic, political and ethnic life of the oasis. One of the largest waves of influx of large numbers of cattle from the steppes of Eurasia was observed in antiquity, especially in the last quarter of the first millennium BC. During this period, some groups of Yuechji, Usun, Hun, and other tribes remained in the cattle-raising areas around the agricultural oases of Sughd and settled there. At the same time, cattle-breeders entered Sughd not only along the Middle Syrdarya, but also through the lower reaches of the Syrdarya - Kyzylkum. These ongoing processes have intensified cultural exchanges between settlers and immigrants. Archaeological evidence from this period shows that the Middle Syrdarya served as a place of communication for different cultures [3].

Numerous burial mounds belonging to cattle-breeders in the Zarafshan oasis have been studied, and the influence of steppe culture on Nakhshab, especially in

antiquity - in the beginning of the 1st millennium BC, has been analyzed. were chronologically divided into three groups [4]. The first group of burial mounds dates back to the VII-III centuries BC, most of which are covered with wood and are simple earthen tombs. The bodies were buried with their heads to the west and covered with reeds (sometimes with a pillow made of reeds). The tomb was also decorated with red paint, chalk sticks, broken pottery, sacrificial stones, swords and daggers [4].

The second group belongs to the II-I centuries BC, and these graves were excavated in a north-south direction, slightly tilted to the west. The bodies were mostly buried southwest, with a hole in the north wall. There are many graves, grains have been dug under the long western wall and stairs have been left. It is separated from the porch by pieces of reeds and limestone.

The third group belongs to the I-VII centuries AD, when it was separated from the porch by a raw brick. Weapons are rare. The bodies were buried in the front (southwest) direction, on a more carpet-like bed. The porridge is the same as before, but now it is below the descent. Until then, the porch and the porch were on the same plane. The burial objects are the same as before - the sheep's forelegs, jars of various shapes, weapons, and sometimes eggs. Traces of fire are observed at the funerals of all groups. There are single and double burials, as well as multi-storey graves and coffins. The corpses were mostly laid on their backs, bent over, with their legs folded at the knees and buried on both sides [5].

The general similarity of the material sources of the ancient Nakhshab mausoleums in the Zarafshan oasis is also observed in the classified ceramic vessels studied on the example of monuments along the Syrdarya River. It also bears a striking resemblance to pottery found in the tombs of herdsmen unearthed in the southern Urals.

A number of features of Nakhshab's history, including the issue of religious relations in the region, are reflected in the medieval Chinese chronicles *Bei Shi* (386-618) and *Sui Shu* (581-618). These chronicles contain some information about the religious beliefs in the Sughd region (Zarafshan and Kashkadarya oases),

Samarkand, Kesh, Nakhshab, Kabudon, Kushaniya. Their scientific study and authenticity are important and relevant not only in the study of the religious views of the peoples living in the Sughd region, but also in the Central Asian region.

These sources are important not only for the socio-political life of the oasis at that time, but also for a relatively complete picture of the entire Central Asian region. In the Chinese chronicles, the administrative units of Sughd are Samarkand (Kan), Bukhara (An, Ansi), Kesh / Shahrisabz (Shy, Shi), Nasaf / Karshi (Nashebo, Nashebolo), Maymurg (Mi), Ishtikhan (Sao). , The geographical location, nature, population of the Kushaniya (Xe) estates, their economic and political life, and some aspects of their religious views [6].

It should be noted that Nakhshab also has some historical information about Buddhism, which describes the relations with India. Of particular importance is the fact that Buddhism in Central Asia has served as a "bridge" in the development of Indian culture and made a significant contribution to the development of cultural ties. By this time, Buddhism had become the center of not only religious but also secular culture between the two regions [7].

It should be noted that the pre-Islamic religious tolerance in the Nakhchivan Valley and Central Asia is confirmed not only on the basis of Chinese chronicles, but also through the Sogdian documents of the Mughal Mountains [8].

There is some information in Chinese chronicles about the religion of Sughd's Kesh property. In particular: - Shy (Kesh), also called Kyuysha and Gyeshuanna. ... There is a temple in Kesh where up to a thousand sheep are slaughtered at each sacrificial ceremony. Prayer is said here before every war ” [9].

This information indicates that Nakhshab was one of the religious centers in its time and that the pilgrims came here with sacrifices and that it was a large temple like Kesh. In addition, Nakhshab is sometimes referred to as a property of Samarkand, and sometimes as a separate province, because Nakhshab is located on the border of Sughd, it is a fertile land and one of the religious centers, and many people from different regions come here to visit. It reinforces the idea that Samarkand has taken control of Kesh.

Conclusions.

Thus, the samples of material culture belonging to the nomads found in the Nakhshab oasis show that from the Bronze Age to the Middle Ages, the cattle-breeding population was constantly entering and settling in the region. These historical processes are also reflected in ancient written sources. From the beginning of the development of the Kashkadarya oasis to its transformation into a densely populated oasis, there was also a place for nomadic pastoral peoples who came and settled over time and lived around the oasis. The herdsmen entered the area along the Lower and Middle Syrdarya, as well as through the ancient Merv, and settled in areas suitable for agriculture. In addition, the religious beliefs of the early Middle Ages (before Islam) in the Nakhshab oasis, the attitude of the population to religion, the information in the Chinese chronicles will undoubtedly help to determine the direction of research in this area. This information will provide us with more insight into our future work.

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